

A Comparative Analysis of Stock Market Cycles

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In this paper, we date the ‘recession’ and ‘expansion’ phases of 46 stock markets around the world from December 1994 to September 2013. We use the Harding and Pagan (2001) methodology to identify peaks and troughs in these stock market indices. This approach enables us to establish periods of synchronization between the markets based on the timing of peaks and troughs and to measure this synchronization by means of the Harding and Pagan (2006) statistic. We find that several recent world crisis episodes and simultaneous recoveries can be identified with this method. We also present evidence demonstrating an increase in the pro-cyclicality of stock markets around the world.

Keywords: stock prices, cycles, synchronization, crisis

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1. Introduction

Business cycles are defined as a series of expansions and contractions of macroeconomic series over time, such as gross domestic product, the unemployment rate, real wages, sales indices or industrial production. Analogously, recently named financial cycles refer to the same types of oscillations identified through financial variables, such as stock market price indices, total loans, or housing price indices. From an econometric perspective, cycles can also be understood as variations occurring in stochastic processes in the middle regions of their frequency domain.

The main objective of this paper is to examine the cycles of stock market prices in 46 countries. We aim to define the cycles’ characteristics in terms of amplitude,

duration and synchronization and explore how those features have changed over the sample period (4th quarter 1994 to 3rd quarter 2013).

Our hypothesis is that emerging countries present idiosyncratic characteristics that differ from developed economies, which have deeper and more liquid capital markets. Nevertheless, the process of globalization and the increases in capital flows between markets over recent decades may have contributed to the homogenization of cycles around the world. In the same vein, we expect financial cycles to show more synchronization as cross-border capital flows increase among economies.

This study can be thought of as a complement to explorations of recent business and financial cycles that aim to clarify several hidden mechanisms in the financial and real sides of economies. This paper does not offer a theoretical explanation of asset price cycles, although it does propose a starting point for future developments in this direction by evaluating the circumstances that describe cycles.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents our hypothesis and its context. Section 3 provides a brief overview of the prior literature on the topic of financial cycles. Section 4 describes the methodological approach followed in the paper. Section 5 contains information about the data used in this study. Section 6 presents the results, and section 7 concludes.

2. Background

The globalization of financial markets has increased considerably over the last three decades due to integration treaties between countries, new technologies, and access to information and new markets. The increase in globalization is evident in cross-border capital flows, which include foreign direct investment, purchases of foreign bonds and equities, and cross-country loans and deposits.

Figure 1 shows that from 1994 to 2012, global cross-border capital flows increased from USD \$841 billion in 1994 to a peak of USD \$6,544 billion in 2007. However, cross-border capital flows decreased after the 2008 financial crisis to USD \$3,287 billion, and by 2012, the amount had only increased to USD \$679 billion. [Figure 1]

According to our initial hypothesis, we expect financial cycles to be more synchronized as cross-border capital flows increase because countries' financial sectors are more integrated. However, we also expect that our empirical results will show a decrease in the synchronization of the cycles after the subprime crisis because of the abrupt diminution of global cross-border flows.

The identification of asset price cycles not only permits an analysis of the synchronization of financial cycles between countries but also allows us to identify periods of booms and recessions in the global economy. Within the time span studied in this paper, three important financial crises occurred: the Asian financial crisis, the dot com crisis and the global financial crisis of 2007-2009.

The 1990s were characterized by an important financial globalization phenomenon that started in 1986 in the London Exchange Market with the opening of the market to financial and corporate enterprises from around the world. Emerging economies experienced an increase in the entry of foreign capital, which in Mexico, for instance, generated a devaluation crisis in 1994-1995.

The crisis in the emerging markets soon arrived in Asia in 1997, causing a financial recession in Thailand, the Philippines, Malaysia, Singapore, Indonesia, Taiwan and South Korea (Marichal, 2010). Further, in 1998, the economies of Brazil and Russia witnessed capital flight and severe devaluations. In 2001, Argentina also experienced a period of economic recession because of external factors.

The United States experienced a boom in its financial market from 1992 to 2001, a period during which there was a high interchange of capital between New York and London. There was also a boom in the derivatives market, and the speculative environment supported extraordinary performances by technological enterprises.

In 2001, the dot com bubble collapsed, and the Fed initiated an expansive monetary policy by increasing the money supply and decreasing the interest rate. This policy fostered an increase in asset prices and housing prices. Because of the large amount of resources available in the economy, more loans were assigned, even to people with a high probability of default. In addition, new financial instruments were created that lacked regulation, with most of them collateralized by subprime mortgages.

By the autumn of 2007, the housing bubble burst, creating a recession in the United States. After the Lehman Brothers collapse, the crisis propagated to the global financial market. The problems of illiquidity and insolvency faced by many countries around the world led to severe impacts in the real sector from 2008 to 2010.

The above factors may have influenced the degree of synchronization of the financial cycles among both developed and undeveloped economies, and these factors should be reflected in several statistical features of the cycles, as noted previously.

3. Related Literature

As highlighted by McDermott and Scott (1999) and Harding and Pagan (2005), the methodologies used to analyze business cycles in prior studies can be divided into two main streams: the growth cycle stream and the classical cycle stream. The growth cycle approach analyzes deviations from a long-run trend of economic activity, while the classical cycle approach aims to find a pattern of expansions and contractions in economic activity.

A large amount of research has been conducted on the real business cycles using the methodologies of the classical cycles (see Rand and Tarp [2002], Cashin [2004], Du Plessis [2006], Male [2011]). However, studies of asset price cycles using this approach are still incipient. Exceptions to this tendency are the studies by Jaeger and Schuknecht (2007) and Agnello and Schuknecht (2011), who used the methodology proposed by Harding and Pagan (2001, 2002) called the triangular method to construct the chronology of boom-bust phases in real asset prices.

The prior literature has instead concentrated on using the growth cycle approach. This approach mainly concerns the appropriate identification of a threshold and the periods in which asset prices exceed it. In each methodology, the researcher must choose among different procedures to filter the series and determine the optimal threshold.

One of the most common methodologies in the literature is the moving average method, which was applied by Bordo and Jeanne (2002), Borio and Lowe (2002), Barajas, Dell'Ariccia, and Levchenko (2007), Mendoza and Terrones (2008), and Fatas et al. (2009). This approach estimates the moving average of a series' returns. The periods in which the average is higher (lower) than a threshold are classified as boom (recession) periods. Gerdesmeier, Reimers, and Roffia (2009) followed the same approach to determine cycles in stock and housing prices, although those authors used a recursive moving average.

Another approach followed in the literature is to estimate the trends of a series using a Hodrick-Prescott filter. With the de-trended data, the booms (recessions) can be identified when the data exceed (are inferior to) a deviation. This approach was followed by Detken and Smets (2004), Adalid and Detken (2007) and Alessi and Detken (2011).

Borgy, Clerc, and Renne (2009) applied all of the above-mentioned methodologies plus two more versions of the Hodrick-Prescott filter and the Band Pass filter. The latter de-trends the data with a Christiano-Fitzgerald band-pass filter to distinguish the peaks and valleys that describe cycles. The authors' objective was to analyze the possibility of determining the span of cycles in stock market prices in a robust way. Based on the identified cycles, macro-prudential policies can be proposed to prevent systemic risk situations. The authors found that using five different methodologies, they were able to date cycles that coincided qualitatively but not quantitatively.

Ponomarenko (2012) applied three methods used in the literature (moving average, the triangular method and the Hodrick-Prescott filter) to determine whether the models designed to predict booms/busts in asset prices for industrialized countries are adequate for emerging economies. He found only 66% consistency between the methods.

In general, the methodologies that are conventionally used in the literature are not robust to determining asset price cycles because each one yields different results. In this sense, dating stock price cycles using a methodology that does not depend on filtration techniques appears to be a promising way to obtain accurate results. This latter approach is followed in this paper by using the classical cycle stream tools.

4. Methodology

4.1. Dating Cycles

To date cycles in stock market prices, we use the methodology originally proposed by Bry and Boschan (1971) to identify business cycles. Recently, Harding and Pagan (2002, 2006) modified this method to accommodate quarterly data, which is the

approach used herein. Since the influential work by these authors, this approach has been applied extensively to date all types of cycles in the financial and economic academic literature (see Canova and Schlaepfer [2012], Male [2011], Drehmann, Borio, and Tsatsaronis [2012], Rand and Tarp [2002]). This approach represents a robust alternative to the filtering techniques frequently employed in this branch of economics given the well-documented pitfalls that can emerge in the construction of an ‘optimal’ filter and the undesirable level of uncertainty associated with the selection of a specific filtering technique in applied work (Canova 1998; 2007).

We consider 46 stock market indices from December 1994 to September 2013, constructed by Morgan Stanley. We selected the sample period with the aim of maximizing the number of markets with complete information in the sample.

The Bry-Boschan methodology can be summarized in the following way: consider an observation y_t , which is a candidate to be a peak of the variable y if $y_t \in \max\{y_{t-2}, y_{t-1}, y_{t+1}, y_{t+2}\}$ and is a candidate to be a trough of the variable y , if $y_t \in \min\{y_{t-2}, y_{t-1}, y_{t+1}, y_{t+2}\}$. To guarantee a meaningful identification, some additional restrictions must be imposed:

- Peaks and troughs should alternate. In case of a violation, the largest peak is retained, and all of the others are eliminated.
- A peak (trough) must be greater (less) than the prior trough (peak).
- The minimum length from peak to peak is 5 quarters.
- The minimum length between peak and trough is 2 quarters.
- Break points that occur between the first two quarters or the last two quarters are eliminated.
- The peaks (troughs) at the beginning or the end that are lower (higher) than the baseline values (final) are eliminated.

4.2. Estimating the Degree of Synchronization

The synchronization analysis of the cycles accords to the statistic proposed by Harding and Pagan (2006):

$$\hat{I} = T^{-1}[\sum_{t=1}^T \mathbf{S}_{xt}\mathbf{S}_{yt} + \sum_{t=1}^T (1 - \mathbf{S}_{xt})(1 - \mathbf{S}_{yt})] \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x}_t and \mathbf{y}_t are series with information about the stock market activity of two different countries, and \mathbf{S}_{xt} and \mathbf{S}_{yt} are binary variables that take the values of 1 and 0 depending on whether the cycle is expansive or contractive, respectively. The concordance index measures the proportion of time that two series are in the same phase; a value of one implies that the two cycles are in the same phase at all times.

To analyze possible changes in the degree of synchronization between the countries' stock cycles, this indicator is estimated on an iterative basis with a moving window of 20 quarters.

Further analysis of synchronization will take place by examining visual patterns of the peaks and troughs to establish the sequence in which different markets enter and exit their recessive and expansive phases.

5. Data

We chose 46 countries to analyze their financial cycles, of which 23 are developed economies and 23 are emerging markets (See Table 1). The countries in the sample were mainly selected because of data availability. The stock price indices used in the analysis are calculated by Morgan Stanley and are called the MSCI Price Index. All of the data were obtained from Datastream. These indices measure the behavior of asset price trades in the stock market of each country without accounting for dividends. The MSCI Price Indices are constructed in a standard way for each country, which permits

comparison among them and the adequate use of the methodology presented in this paper.

[Table 1]

The frequency of the data is quarterly, and the sample period starts in the 4th quarter of 1994 and finishes in the 3rd quarter 2013.

To obtain a general perspective of the stock market characteristics of each country, the relative market capitalization and market concentration are reported in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively. The relative market capitalization measure indicates that on average, the developed markets (148%) are larger than the emerging markets (59%). The market concentration shows that the emerging markets (52%) are on average more concentrated than the developed markets (43%).

Hence, the analysis of the characteristics of the stock market asset prices of the countries in the sample must consider that the emerging countries still have underdeveloped markets that are less deep and more concentrated than the markets of the developed economies. These differences should be reflected in the characteristics of the cycles of each group of countries.

[Figure 2]

[Figure 3]

6. Results

6.1. Characteristics of the Estimated Cycles

6.1.1. Duration of the Cycle

The results regarding the duration of the cycles (Table 2) indicate that on average, for both the developed and the emerging markets, the expansion phase lasts longer than the contraction phase. Thus, the estimated financial cycles are in accordance with the

stylized facts from real business cycles, which indicate that cycles are generally asymmetric, with expansions longer than recessions.

However, the duration of both the expansion phase and the recession phase is longer in developed countries than in emerging economies, indicating a longer duration of cycles in developed countries. The results for emerging markets may indicate a more volatile pattern of cycles in such countries, which could be a consequence of greater volatility in the financial flows arriving in emerging economies because such economies present a lesser degree of market development than developed countries (See Figures 2 and 3). According to Male (2011), this result is not in accordance with the behavior of the real business cycle. The author concluded that there are no significant differences between the duration of the GDP cycle in developed and emerging countries.

[Table 2]

Table 3 shows the average duration of the financial cycles for each of the countries in the sample. It is interesting to note that the average duration of the expansion phase in Hong Kong's cycles: it lasted 20.50 quarters, while the recession phase lasted for only 6.30 quarters. This result coincides with Hong Kong's large relative market capitalization (1078%), which is the largest of the developed economies in the sample. In the same fashion, in the set of emerging countries, the largest markets tend to simultaneously have the longest durations of phases. For instance, South Africa had an average expansion duration of 9.80 quarters and only 4 quarters in its contraction phases.

[Table 3]

6.1.2. Amplitude of the Cycle

The average amplitude of the asset price cycles measures the changes in stock market activity; in other words, this measure indicates the depth of the expansion and

contraction phases. Tables 4 and 5 show the aggregate and individual statistics for each group of countries. In the two sets of economies, the average amplitude of the expansion phase is similar to that of the contraction phase.

However, similar to the average duration, the average amplitude of the phases in developed countries is significantly greater than that in the emerging economies. This result is also consistent with the fact that developed countries have deeper, more liquid and less concentrated stock markets. Therefore, they tend to experience greater and more sustainable growth rates in their stock markets, allowing them to expand in a more uniform fashion.

In Male's (2011) real business cycle analysis, the author found the opposite results. Emerging countries experienced a greater average duration than the developed countries, which explained the greater growth rates in the emerging economies.

[Table 4]

[Table 5]

6.2.Synchronization of Cycles

Figure 4 shows the means of the synchronization statistics for the 46 countries in our sample from September 1999 to September 2013. These results were obtained after calculating each statistic for every pair of countries using information for 20 quarters. Then, the statistics were averaged transversally to obtain each point in the plot. Note that one step forward in the x-axis indicates that the next 20 quarters, starting one quarter later and ending one quarter later, were used to construct the statistic. In this way, it is possible to describe the synchronization in the sample during the period under analysis using a single dotted line. The statistic lies between 0 and 1 by construction, where values above 0 and below 0.5 are an indicator of discordant cycles, and values above 0.5 indicate that the cycles co-move in the same direction most of the time.

[Figure 4]

As shown in Figure 4, the stock market cycles gained synchronization from the beginning of the sample period, in approximately 1999, to the start of the global financial crisis in 2007-2008, increasing from values under 0.54 to over 0.64. After the crisis, the synchronization between the markets seemed to revert to lower levels of approximately 0.62, and it remained near this value until the end of the sample. That result is consistent with the original hypothesis described in the introduction. Following the general idea presented there, we can state that the changing direction of financial flows between economies during the first decade of the century determined the emergence of booms and crashes simultaneously around the world and in turn caused an increasing degree of synchronization between stock market prices. However, the crisis acted as an atomizer and caused a reduction in synchronization once it spread to all of the different markets, leaving no market unaffected.

Nevertheless, it has to be notice that, although the first increment in the average synchronization of the full sample is statistically significant at any traditional confidence level ($t = -2.36$), the subsequent decreasing is not ($t = 0.76$). Therefore more empirical evidence is required before concluding in favor of the atomization hypothesis at the end of the sample.

As can be seen from Figures 5 and 6, synchronization mainly arose because of the increases in concordance among the emerging economies and between the emerging economies and the developed economies, given that synchronization remained relatively unaltered throughout the sample span among the 23 developed economies in our sample.

In the latter case the mean statistic went from 0.59 in September 1999 to 0.63 in September 2013. The reason to observe less sensitive synchronization statistics within

the developed economies than those between the emerging markets might be related to the greater size and liquidity of the developed markets. These features may help to explain why the mature markets seem more depended on idiosyncratic shocks and less dependent on international flows and portfolio reallocation considerations, following the portfolio movements by international financial investors.

[Figure 5]

[Figure 6]

6.3. Identification of Financial Crises

Figure 7 details the timing of the asset price cycles by illustrating the peaks (P) and valleys (V) estimated for each market. A peak indicates that the market is entering a contraction phase, while a valley indicates that the market is entering an expansion phase. Therefore, between a peak and a valley the market is in a recession, and between a valley and a peak the market is in a boom.

There is a clear concordance between the timing of the peaks and valleys of the markets during the period studied. This concordance allows the identification of several financial crises.

The Asian crisis can be identified in 1996 and 1997. The stock markets of Japan and Singapore were the first to enter a recession phase in June 1996, followed by Malaysia in March 1997, and in the next quarter, these countries were followed by Hong Kong, Indonesia and Taiwan. The expansion of the crisis to other countries such as Brazil and Russia can also be identified in our results.

Male (2011) also identified the Asian crisis in the real business cycles of 32 emerging countries and three developed countries. However, the economies entered the recession phase at the end of 1997 and the beginning of 1998, which indicates that peaks in financial cycles act as a leading indicator of peaks in the real cycles.

In the 2000-2001 dot com crisis, 27 markets entered a contraction phase, including the United States in December 2001. From 2001 to 2006, there is no clear pattern in the timing of peaks and valleys. However, in 2007 and 2008, 28 markets entered a recession phase, including 12 developed countries (including the United States and the United Kingdom) and 16 emerging economies. This evidence is consistent with our results of the synchronization presented in section 6.2: before the subprime crisis, the degree of synchronization between all of the countries in the sample was high, and consequently many markets experienced a recession in their financial markets at the same time.

In 2009, 32 markets entered an expansion phase in their cycles; however during this period, the effects of the financial crisis spread to the real sector. Hence, even though the stock markets recovered rapidly, the real sector continued in a recession phase. In other words, we can state that financial crises, in this case, crises in the stock markets, precede crises in the real sector.

Finally, in 2011 and 2012, many of the markets entered a recession phase and later an expansion phase. This result can be explained by the turmoil in several European economies and lags from the 2008 subprime crisis.

[Figure 7]

7. Conclusions

The Harding and Pagan methodology is generally used to date peaks and troughs of real quarterly variables without reverting to filtering techniques. The approach is very useful to date real cycles, and several authors have employed it recently to date financial cycles as well. Within this trend, the analysis of stock market cycles promises to be very informative and remains rarely studied.

This paper advances research in that direction. Expansion and recessions phases are identified for 46 economies, of which 23 are emerging markets and 23 are developed markets. The analysis allows us to identify several idiosyncratic characteristics of financial-stock cycles. For instance, the average duration and amplitude of financial cycles in the developed markets are greater than those in emerging markets. This result contrasts with what has been reported in prior studies regarding the trends of real cycles. Real cycles tend to have a larger amplitude in emerging economies and therefore serve as to explain their relatively larger growth rates in recent decades in relation to the growth rates in developed countries. The developed markets tend to experience more sustainable growth paths in their stock market values. This result can be explained by developed markets' better indicators in terms of size, liquidity and concentration in comparison to emerging markets.

We are also able to present evidence in favor of our starting hypothesis, namely, that globalization and subsequent increases in capital flows between economies could have helped to increase the degree of synchronization between the world's stock markets. Using a synchronization statistic, we found that pro-cyclicality among the markets indeed experienced a significant increase from the mid-1990s to 2008. After this period, the degree of synchronization stabilized to a lower value, following the same trend documented in global capital flows.

A final aspect of our study concerns the analysis of the detected peaks and troughs, which may help to identify financial crises in the world. In fact, the peaks in financial cycles act as a leading indicator of the peaks in the real cycles, which once again highlights the importance of their study and comprehension.

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Table 1. List of Countries and Their Acronyms

DEVELOPED COUNTRIES		EMERGING COUNTRIES	
US	United States	MA	Morocco
JP	Japan	LK	Sri Lanka
DE	Germany	PK	Pakistan
GB	United Kingdom	IN	India
AU	Australia	CN	China
FR	France	BR	Brazil
IT	Italy	ZA	South Africa
SG	Singapore	ID	Indonesia
CA	Canada	MY	Malaysia
ES	Spain	MX	Mexico
CH	Switzerland	RU	Russian Federation
HK	Hong Kong	TW	Taiwan
NL	Netherlands	AR	Argentina
SE	Sweden	CO	Colombia
AT	Austria	CZ	Czech Republic
BE	Belgium	HU	Hungary
FI	Finland	TH	Thailand
NZ	New Zealand	TR	Turkey
NO	Norway	CL	Chile
PT	Portugal	EG	Egypt
DK	Denmark	PE	Peru
IE	Ireland	PL	Poland
IL	Israel	KR	Republic of Korea

Table 2. Duration Descriptive Statistics

Developed Countries	Duration (quarters)		
	Expansion	Contraction	Financial Cycle
Average	9.82	6.43	16.24
Maximun	20.50	12.00	28.00
Minimun	4.00	3.80	10.70
Emerging Countries	Duration (quarters)		
	Expansion	Contraction	Financial Cycle
Average	7.76	5.73	13.49
Maximun	10.20	9.80	19.50
Minimun	4.10	3.00	7.70

Table 3. Average Duration

Developed Countries	Average Duration (quarters)			Emerging Countries	Average Duration (quarters)		
	Expansion	Contraction	Financial Cycle		Expansion	Contraction	Financial Cycle
United States	6.20	4.60	10.80	Morocco	8.30	8.30	16.60
Japan	4.80	6.50	11.30	Sri Lanka	9.00	6.20	15.20
Germany	19.00	9.00	28.00	Pakistan	9.00	3.00	12.00
United Kingdom	8.80	5.00	13.80	India	7.00	4.40	11.40
Australia	12.00	4.20	16.20	China	5.70	4.70	10.40
France	10.50	5.50	16.00	Brasil	4.70	5.20	9.90
Italy	7.50	12.00	19.50	South Africa	9.80	4.00	13.80
Singapore	10.80	4.00	14.80	Indonesia	7.50	8.20	15.70
Canada	8.70	7.00	15.70	Malaysia	10.00	4.50	14.50
Spain	10.00	10.00	20.00	Mexico	8.00	4.20	12.20
Switzerland	6.80	6.40	13.20	Russian Federation	4.80	5.10	9.90
Hong Kong	20.50	6.30	26.80	Taiwan	7.00	6.00	13.00
Netherlands	11.70	6.70	18.40	Argentina	8.60	3.80	12.40
Sweden	18.50	5.30	23.80	Colombia	8.60	6.20	14.80
Austria	11.70	10.30	22.00	Czech Republic	9.20	6.50	15.70
Belgium	8.00	7.50	15.50	Hungary	9.70	9.80	19.50
Finland	7.20	3.80	11.00	Thailand	10.20	7.50	17.70
New Zealand	8.80	4.80	13.60	Turkey	9.50	7.00	16.50
Norway	5.00	6.20	11.20	Chile	7.60	5.80	13.40
Portugal	4.00	6.70	10.70	Egypt	4.80	9.80	14.60
Denmark	9.00	4.80	13.80	Peru	8.80	3.60	12.40
Ireland	9.00	6.80	15.80	Poland	6.50	4.50	11.00
Israel	7.30	4.40	11.70	Republic of Korea	4.10	3.60	7.70

Table 4. Amplitude Descriptive Statistics

Developed Countries	Amplitude (index units)	
	Expansion	Contraction
Average	86.69	85.67
Maximun	165.50	134.00
Minimun	31.00	35.80

Emerging Countries	Amplitude (index units)	
	Expansion	Contraction
Average	43.01	41.50
Maximun	72.80	68.80
Minimun	21.80	21.00

Table 5. Average Amplitude

Developed Countries	Average Amplitude (index units)		Emerging Countries	Average Amplitude (index units)	
	Expansion	Contraction		Expansion	Contraction
United States	130.6	128.60	Morocco	28.7	21.00
Japan	89.0	89.80	Sri Lanka	51.8	38.20
Germany	118.0	108.50	Pakistan	40.2	32.60
United Kingdom	64.5	60.80	India	32.3	23.80
Australia	76.5	76.00	China	24.3	26.20
France	101.2	128.80	Brasil	28.3	35.30
Italy	104.0	104.30	South Africa	27.2	27.40
Singapore	82.0	90.80	Indonesia	55.2	64.50
Canada	31.0	50.50	Malasyia	49.3	44.20
Spain	165.5	131.70	Mexico	31.4	33.80
Switzerland	111.8	122.60	Russian Federation	35.6	28.10
Hong Kong	80.0	108.00	Taiwan	62.6	59.20
Netherlands	132.0	134.00	Argentina	72.8	68.80
Sweden	144.0	89.70	Colombia	47.6	44.50
Austria	57.7	53.70	Czech Republic	21.8	31.20
Belgium	86.0	76.80	Hungary	43.0	50.80
Finland	70.2	70.00	Thailand	60.0	60.50
New Zeland	73.2	54.00	Turkey	57.8	58.20
Norway	85.4	87.30	Chile	43.8	34.80
Portugal	36.0	35.80	Egypt	53.8	45.80
Denmark	55.0	61.40	Peru	34.0	39.60
Ireland	55.0	62.80	Poland	52.2	58.00
Israel	45.3	44.60	Republic of Korea	35.6	28.10

(1) Figure 1. Global Cross-border Capital Flows, 1980-2012

Note: USD \$billion, constant 2012 exchange rates

Note: Source IMF Balance of Payments

Note: Global cross-border capital flows include foreign direct investment, purchases of foreign bonds and equities, cross-border loans and deposits and reserves

(2) Figure 2. Relative Market Capitalization, 2012

Note: Source own elaboration with data from the World Federation of Exchange and the World Bank DataBank

Note: This figure measures the size of each stock market based on the country's domestic market capitalization (total number of shares traded multiplied by their market value) divided by its GDP.

Note: Domestic market capitalization was taken from the World Federation of Exchanges, and the GDP data were derived from the World Bank. Data for the markets of Italy, Taiwan, Sri Lanka and Pakistan were not available. The information from the Euronext Stock Exchange included the stock exchanges of France (Euronext Paris), the Netherlands (Euronext Amsterdam), Belgium (Euronext Brussels) and Portugal (Euronext Lisboa). The information from the NASDAQ OMX Nordic Exchange included the stock exchanges of Sweden (NASDAQ Stockholm), Finland (NASDAQ Helsinki), Denmark (NASDAQ Copenhagen) and Ireland (NASDAQ Iceland).

(3) Figure 3. Market Concentration, 2012

Note: Source own elaboration with data from the World Federation of Exchange

Note: This figure measures the concentration of the markets based on the percentage of the 10 listed firms with the highest domestic market capitalizations over the total capitalization of the market.

Note: Data for the markets of Canada, Italy, New Zealand, Sri Lanka and Pakistan were not available.

(4) Figure 4. Mean of the Synchronization Statistics, Full Sample

Note: Source own elaboration.

(5) Figure 5. Mean of the Synchronization Statistics, Developed Countries

Note: Source own elaboration.

Appendix 1. Synchronization Matrix

[Figure 8]

COUNTRIES		DEVELOPED COUNTRIES																						
		US	JP	DE	GB	AU	FR	IT	SG	CA	ES	CH	HK	NL	SE	AT	BE	FI	NZ	NO	PT	DK	IE	IL
DEVELOPED COUNTRIES	US	1.00	0.58	0.46	0.45	0.39	0.51	0.49	0.67	0.46	0.41	0.43	0.39	0.46	0.49	0.54	0.41	0.50	0.45	0.47	0.51	0.57	0.53	0.54
	JP	0.58	1.00	0.62	0.61	0.55	0.59	0.54	0.54	0.49	0.46	0.72	0.61	0.59	0.57	0.57	0.59	0.55	0.53	0.58	0.64	0.78	0.55	0.59
	DE	0.46	0.62	1.00	0.88	0.67	0.61	0.55	0.61	0.58	0.66	0.66	0.83	0.71	0.61	0.68	0.68	0.72	0.62	0.59	0.58	0.79	0.72	0.66
	GB	0.45	0.61	0.88	1.00	0.61	0.67	0.51	0.57	0.62	0.54	0.62	0.76	0.59	0.57	0.67	0.67	0.68	0.55	0.58	0.57	0.80	0.66	0.62
	AU	0.39	0.55	0.67	0.61	1.00	0.57	0.49	0.62	0.57	0.64	0.70	0.76	0.64	0.62	0.54	0.67	0.66	0.71	0.39	0.49	0.64	0.66	0.64
	FR	0.51	0.59	0.61	0.67	0.57	1.00	0.39	0.63	0.39	0.58	0.53	0.70	0.47	0.55	0.63	0.53	0.64	0.43	0.41	0.42	0.66	0.43	0.61
	IT	0.49	0.54	0.55	0.51	0.49	0.39	1.00	0.50	0.66	0.45	0.26	0.59	0.39	0.45	0.32	0.66	0.46	0.54	0.59	0.58	0.61	0.43	0.45
	SG	0.67	0.54	0.61	0.57	0.62	0.63	0.50	1.00	0.42	0.53	0.42	0.59	0.61	0.58	0.58	0.50	0.57	0.57	0.41	0.50	0.63	0.57	0.68
	CA	0.46	0.49	0.58	0.62	0.57	0.39	0.66	0.42	1.00	0.55	0.50	0.49	0.39	0.63	0.39	0.82	0.59	0.57	0.70	0.53	0.63	0.62	0.47
	ES	0.41	0.46	0.66	0.54	0.64	0.58	0.45	0.53	0.55	1.00	0.61	0.67	0.55	0.53	0.53	0.61	0.78	0.51	0.57	0.50	0.50	0.62	0.53
	CH	0.43	0.72	0.66	0.62	0.70	0.53	0.26	0.42	0.50	0.61	1.00	0.59	0.74	0.68	0.68	0.55	0.70	0.54	0.54	0.55	0.58	0.72	0.63
	HK	0.39	0.61	0.83	0.76	0.76	0.70	0.59	0.59	0.49	0.67	0.59	1.00	0.70	0.59	0.62	0.62	0.68	0.58	0.42	0.59	0.78	0.61	0.57
	NL	0.46	0.59	0.71	0.59	0.64	0.47	0.39	0.61	0.39	0.55	0.74	0.70	1.00	0.63	0.74	0.45	0.57	0.59	0.54	0.71	0.61	0.72	0.63
	SE	0.49	0.57	0.61	0.57	0.62	0.55	0.45	0.58	0.63	0.53	0.68	0.59	0.63	1.00	0.58	0.63	0.70	0.70	0.57	0.42	0.55	0.70	0.47
AT	0.54	0.57	0.68	0.67	0.54	0.63	0.32	0.58	0.39	0.53	0.68	0.62	0.74	0.58	1.00	0.45	0.54	0.46	0.54	0.61	0.55	0.67	0.61	
BE	0.41	0.59	0.68	0.67	0.67	0.53	0.66	0.50	0.82	0.61	0.55	0.62	0.45	0.63	0.45	1.00	0.64	0.67	0.57	0.50	0.68	0.70	0.61	
FI	0.50	0.55	0.72	0.68	0.66	0.64	0.46	0.57	0.59	0.78	0.70	0.68	0.57	0.70	0.54	0.64	1.00	0.61	0.55	0.49	0.62	0.71	0.57	
NZ	0.45	0.53	0.62	0.55	0.71	0.43	0.54	0.57	0.57	0.51	0.54	0.58	0.59	0.70	0.46	0.67	0.61	1.00	0.45	0.51	0.54	0.66	0.51	
NO	0.47	0.58	0.59	0.58	0.39	0.41	0.39	0.41	0.70	0.57	0.54	0.42	0.54	0.57	0.54	0.57	0.55	0.45	1.00	0.59	0.51	0.55	0.46	
PT	0.51	0.64	0.58	0.57	0.49	0.42	0.58	0.50	0.53	0.50	0.55	0.59	0.71	0.42	0.61	0.50	0.49	0.51	0.59	1.00	0.68	0.57	0.53	
DK	0.57	0.78	0.79	0.80	0.64	0.66	0.61	0.63	0.63	0.50	0.58	0.78	0.61	0.55	0.55	0.68	0.62	0.54	0.51	0.68	1.00	0.62	0.61	
IE	0.53	0.55	0.72	0.66	0.66	0.43	0.43	0.57	0.62	0.62	0.72	0.61	0.72	0.70	0.67	0.70	0.71	0.66	0.55	0.57	0.62	1.00	0.62	
IL	0.54	0.59	0.66	0.62	0.64	0.61	0.45	0.68	0.47	0.53	0.63	0.57	0.63	0.47	0.61	0.61	0.57	0.51	0.46	0.53	0.61	0.62	1.00	
EMERGING COUNTRIES	MA	0.42	0.53	0.70	0.58	0.61	0.46	0.36	0.54	0.43	0.57	0.72	0.61	0.88	0.57	0.80	0.46	0.53	0.55	0.55	0.70	0.54	0.71	0.62
	LK	0.63	0.61	0.64	0.71	0.50	0.64	0.59	0.64	0.46	0.46	0.49	0.61	0.59	0.54	0.62	0.57	0.58	0.47	0.55	0.51	0.64	0.66	0.62
	PK	0.64	0.57	0.66	0.62	0.62	0.61	0.63	0.74	0.50	0.45	0.42	0.62	0.55	0.58	0.61	0.58	0.49	0.59	0.49	0.45	0.63	0.54	0.68
	IN	0.64	0.62	0.58	0.64	0.51	0.63	0.53	0.68	0.45	0.42	0.47	0.59	0.61	0.50	0.58	0.45	0.46	0.46	0.49	0.61	0.66	0.46	0.66
	CN	0.62	0.57	0.61	0.64	0.57	0.58	0.37	0.53	0.50	0.47	0.58	0.57	0.61	0.55	0.68	0.55	0.59	0.62	0.49	0.63	0.63	0.59	0.61
	BR	0.39	0.63	0.67	0.61	0.61	0.57	0.54	0.49	0.54	0.62	0.64	0.68	0.70	0.51	0.54	0.64	0.58	0.47	0.53	0.70	0.64	0.61	0.75
	ZA	0.43	0.59	0.76	0.75	0.80	0.58	0.34	0.58	0.63	0.66	0.82	0.72	0.68	0.68	0.63	0.66	0.72	0.54	0.46	0.53	0.74	0.78	0.61
	ID	0.32	0.55	0.62	0.66	0.45	0.43	0.67	0.33	0.72	0.43	0.51	0.61	0.49	0.59	0.38	0.70	0.55	0.55	0.63	0.57	0.62	0.53	0.41
	MY	0.51	0.70	0.82	0.80	0.59	0.63	0.63	0.58	0.61	0.50	0.58	0.83	0.63	0.61	0.58	0.61	0.62	0.49	0.51	0.66	0.87	0.59	0.58
	MX	0.53	0.61	0.75	0.79	0.55	0.64	0.54	0.62	0.67	0.54	0.57	0.68	0.64	0.62	0.57	0.64	0.66	0.53	0.66	0.67	0.78	0.66	0.62
	RU	0.57	0.62	0.55	0.57	0.49	0.53	0.58	0.42	0.63	0.32	0.55	0.49	0.47	0.61	0.61	0.58	0.51	0.59	0.62	0.53	0.58	0.59	0.47
	TW	0.57	0.62	0.68	0.78	0.54	0.71	0.47	0.55	0.58	0.63	0.53	0.70	0.53	0.47	0.58	0.58	0.62	0.46	0.54	0.58	0.76	0.54	0.58
	AR	0.42	0.58	0.67	0.66	0.63	0.72	0.51	0.70	0.54	0.59	0.57	0.76	0.70	0.64	0.59	0.57	0.61	0.50	0.53	0.59	0.70	0.58	0.54
	CO	0.47	0.47	0.54	0.66	0.47	0.57	0.57	0.51	0.67	0.36	0.51	0.50	0.49	0.64	0.49	0.67	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.46	0.57	0.55	0.59
	CZ	0.59	0.67	0.68	0.57	0.54	0.58	0.53	0.68	0.39	0.53	0.61	0.64	0.74	0.47	0.53	0.50	0.57	0.43	0.49	0.68	0.71	0.62	0.79
	HU	0.45	0.58	0.54	0.58	0.45	0.43	0.80	0.46	0.64	0.30	0.38	0.53	0.43	0.46	0.36	0.62	0.34	0.42	0.61	0.57	0.64	0.45	0.43
	TH	0.64	0.72	0.66	0.62	0.46	0.50	0.53	0.66	0.42	0.37	0.58	0.57	0.74	0.63	0.66	0.42	0.49	0.51	0.62	0.66	0.71	0.57	0.55
	TR	0.54	0.75	0.66	0.64	0.54	0.58	0.53	0.68	0.45	0.45	0.61	0.62	0.71	0.55	0.53	0.50	0.54	0.43	0.54	0.68	0.76	0.59	0.63
CH	0.58	0.55	0.64	0.58	0.61	0.38	0.46	0.57	0.43	0.46	0.67	0.53	0.75	0.59	0.64	0.51	0.61	0.66	0.55	0.62	0.54	0.74	0.70	
EG	0.47	0.63	0.51	0.53	0.47	0.59	0.57	0.41	0.49	0.43	0.54	0.53	0.46	0.46	0.57	0.62	0.45	0.45	0.50	0.49	0.57	0.53	0.43	
PE	0.53	0.61	0.67	0.66	0.63	0.67	0.43	0.64	0.57	0.51	0.64	0.74	0.70	0.67	0.59	0.54	0.66	0.55	0.42	0.62	0.72	0.58	0.57	
PL	0.46	0.67	0.71	0.75	0.59	0.55	0.45	0.53	0.58	0.50	0.66	0.64	0.63	0.55	0.55	0.58	0.62	0.64	0.54	0.68	0.76	0.59	0.58	
KR	0.47	0.63	0.59	0.68	0.61	0.54	0.49	0.57	0.41	0.38	0.59	0.55	0.57	0.41	0.59	0.49	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.59	0.67	0.45	0.72	

COUNTRIES		EMERGING COUNTRIES																						
		MA	LK	PK	IN	CN	BR	ZA	ID	MY	MX	RU	TW	AR	CO	CZ	HU	TH	TR	CL	EG	PE	PL	KR
DEVELOPED COUNTRIES	US	0.42	0.63	0.64	0.64	0.62	0.39	0.43	0.32	0.51	0.53	0.57	0.57	0.42	0.47	0.59	0.45	0.64	0.54	0.58	0.47	0.53	0.46	0.47
	JP	0.53	0.61	0.57	0.62	0.57	0.63	0.59	0.55	0.70	0.61	0.62	0.62	0.58	0.47	0.67	0.58	0.72	0.75	0.55	0.63	0.61	0.67	0.63
	DE	0.70	0.64	0.66	0.58	0.61	0.67	0.76	0.62	0.82	0.75	0.55	0.68	0.67	0.54	0.68	0.54	0.66	0.66	0.64	0.51	0.67	0.71	0.59
	GB	0.58	0.71	0.62	0.64	0.64	0.61	0.75	0.66	0.80	0.79	0.57	0.78	0.66	0.66	0.57	0.58	0.62	0.64	0.58	0.53	0.66	0.75	0.68
	AU	0.61	0.50	0.62	0.51	0.57	0.61	0.80	0.45	0.59	0.55	0.49	0.54	0.63	0.47	0.54	0.45	0.46	0.54	0.61	0.47	0.63	0.59	0.61
	FR	0.46	0.64	0.61	0.63	0.58	0.57	0.58	0.43	0.63	0.64	0.53	0.71	0.72	0.57	0.58	0.43	0.50	0.58	0.38	0.59	0.67	0.55	0.54
	IT	0.36	0.59	0.63	0.53	0.37	0.54	0.34	0.67	0.63	0.54	0.58	0.47	0.51	0.57	0.53	0.80	0.53	0.53	0.46	0.57	0.43	0.45	0.49
	SG	0.54	0.64	0.74	0.68	0.53	0.49	0.58	0.33	0.58	0.62	0.42	0.55	0.70	0.51	0.68	0.46	0.66	0.68	0.57	0.41	0.64	0.53	0.57
	CA	0.43	0.46	0.50	0.45	0.50	0.54	0.63	0.72	0.61	0.67	0.63	0.58	0.54	0.67	0.39	0.64	0.42	0.45	0.43	0.49	0.57	0.58	0.41
	ES	0.57	0.46	0.45	0.42	0.47	0.62	0.66	0.43	0.50	0.54	0.32	0.63	0.59	0.36	0.53	0.30	0.37	0.45	0.46	0.43	0.51	0.50	0.38
	CH	0.72	0.49	0.42	0.47	0.58	0.64	0.82	0.51	0.58	0.57	0.55	0.53	0.57	0.51	0.61	0.38	0.58	0.61	0.67	0.54	0.64	0.66	0.59
	HK	0.61	0.61	0.62	0.59	0.57	0.68	0.72	0.61	0.83	0.68	0.49	0.70	0.76	0.50	0.64	0.53	0.57	0.62	0.53	0.53	0.74	0.64	0.55
	NL	0.88	0.59	0.55	0.61	0.61	0.70	0.68	0.49	0.63	0.64	0.47	0.53	0.70	0.49	0.74	0.43	0.74	0.71	0.75	0.46	0.70	0.63	0.57
	SE	0.57	0.54	0.58	0.50	0.55	0.51	0.68	0.59	0.61	0.62	0.61	0.47	0.64	0.64	0.47	0.46	0.63	0.55	0.59	0.46	0.67	0.55	0.41
	AT	0.80	0.62	0.61	0.58	0.68	0.54	0.63	0.38	0.58	0.57	0.61	0.58	0.59	0.49	0.53	0.36	0.66	0.53	0.64	0.57	0.59	0.55	0.59
	BE	0.46	0.57	0.58	0.45	0.55	0.64	0.66	0.70	0.61	0.64	0.58	0.58	0.57	0.67	0.50	0.62	0.42	0.50	0.51	0.62	0.54	0.58	0.49
	FI	0.53	0.58	0.49	0.46	0.59	0.58	0.72	0.55	0.62	0.66	0.51	0.62	0.61	0.53	0.57	0.34	0.49	0.54	0.61	0.45	0.66	0.62	0.47
	NZ	0.55	0.47	0.59	0.46	0.62	0.47	0.54	0.55	0.49	0.53	0.59	0.46	0.50	0.53	0.43	0.42	0.51	0.43	0.66	0.45	0.55	0.64	0.47
NO	0.55	0.55	0.49	0.49	0.49	0.53	0.46	0.63	0.51	0.66	0.62	0.54	0.53	0.53	0.49	0.61	0.62	0.54	0.55	0.50	0.42	0.54	0.47	
PT	0.70	0.51	0.45	0.61	0.63	0.70	0.53	0.57	0.66	0.67	0.53	0.58	0.59	0.46	0.68	0.57	0.66	0.68	0.62	0.49	0.62	0.68	0.59	
DK	0.54	0.64	0.63	0.66	0.63	0.64	0.74	0.62	0.87	0.78	0.58	0.76	0.70	0.57	0.71	0.64	0.71	0.76	0.54	0.57	0.72	0.76	0.67	
IE	0.71	0.66	0.54	0.46	0.59	0.61	0.78	0.53	0.59	0.66	0.59	0.54	0.58	0.55	0.62	0.45	0.57	0.59	0.74	0.53	0.58	0.59	0.45	
IL	0.62	0.62	0.68	0.66	0.61	0.75	0.61	0.41	0.58	0.62	0.47	0.58	0.54	0.59	0.79	0.43	0.55	0.63	0.70	0.43	0.57	0.58	0.72	
EMERGING COUNTRIES	MA	1.00	0.50	0.49	0.51	0.57	0.68	0.67	0.47	0.57	0.61	0.51	0.46	0.63	0.42	0.64	0.45	0.64	0.62	0.74	0.45	0.66	0.62	0.53
	LK	0.50	1.00	0.75	0.80	0.59	0.61	0.57	0.55	0.67	0.71	0.62	0.72	0.63	0.71	0.64	0.58	0.70	0.75	0.66	0.66	0.58	0.59	0.63
	PK	0.49	0.75	1.00	0.74	0.58	0.54	0.55	0.46	0.63	0.59	0.58	0.61	0.59	0.62	0.61	0.57	0.63	0.61	0.57	0.51	0.51	0.53	0.57
	IN	0.51	0.80	0.74	1.00	0.66	0.62	0.55	0.49	0.68	0.78	0.53	0.76	0.70	0.70	0.68	0.54	0.76	0.79	0.64	0.54	0.70	0.68	0.72
	CN	0.57	0.59	0.58	0.66	1.00	0.57	0.58	0.51	0.55	0.62	0.55	0.66	0.49	0.62	0.50	0.28	0.61	0.53	0.67	0.43	0.59	0.63	0.64
	BR	0.68	0.61	0.54	0.62	0.57	1.00	0.64	0.63	0.70	0.68	0.49	0.59	0.63	0.61	0.80	0.58	0.57	0.72	0.63	0.55	0.68	0.59	0.63
	ZA	0.67	0.57	0.55	0.55	0.58	0.64	1.00	0.54	0.71	0.70	0.53	0.66	0.70	0.57	0.61	0.46	0.55	0.66	0.62	0.51	0.72	0.71	0.59
	ID	0.47	0.55	0.46	0.49	0.51	0.63	0.54	1.00	0.67	0.63	0.59	0.57	0.58	0.74	0.46	0.71	0.54	0.57	0.47	0.58	0.58	0.62	0.50
	MY	0.57	0.67	0.63	0.68	0.55	0.70	0.71	0.67	1.00	0.78	0.61	0.74	0.72	0.62	0.71	0.67	0.71	0.76	0.54	0.51	0.78	0.71	0.62
	MX	0.61	0.71	0.59	0.78	0.62	0.68	0.70	0.63	0.78	1.00	0.59	0.75	0.82	0.71	0.72	0.61	0.70	0.78	0.63	0.55	0.76	0.78	0.58
	RU	0.51	0.62	0.58	0.53	0.55	0.49	0.53	0.59	0.61	0.59	1.00	0.50	0.51	0.67	0.47	0.64	0.61	0.50	0.62	0.67	0.62	0.61	0.54
	TW	0.46	0.72	0.61	0.76	0.66	0.59	0.66	0.57	0.74	0.75	0.50	1.00	0.64	0.62	0.55	0.46	0.55	0.63	0.49	0.51	0.64	0.71	0.62
	AR	0.63	0.63	0.59	0.70	0.49	0.63	0.70	0.58	0.72	0.82	0.51	0.64	1.00	0.66	0.67	0.58	0.64	0.75	0.50	0.58	0.82	0.67	0.47
	CO	0.42	0.71	0.62	0.70	0.62	0.61	0.57	0.74	0.62	0.71	0.67	0.62	0.66	1.00	0.54	0.61	0.57	0.62	0.58	0.63	0.66	0.62	0.61
	CZ	0.64	0.64	0.61	0.68	0.50	0.80	0.61	0.46	0.71	0.72	0.47	0.55	0.67	0.54	1.00	0.59	0.71	0.84	0.67	0.54	0.67	0.63	0.64
	HU	0.45	0.58	0.57	0.54	0.28	0.58	0.46	0.71	0.67	0.61	0.64	0.46	0.58	0.61	0.59	1.00	0.59	0.64	0.45	0.66	0.53	0.51	0.55
	TH	0.64	0.70	0.63	0.76	0.61	0.57	0.55	0.54	0.71	0.70	0.61	0.55	0.64	0.57	0.71	0.59	1.00	0.82	0.75	0.54	0.64	0.66	0.70
	TR	0.62	0.75	0.61	0.79	0.53	0.72	0.66	0.57	0.76	0.78	0.50	0.63	0.75	0.62	0.84	0.64	0.82	1.00	0.64	0.57	0.72	0.71	0.67
	CH	0.74	0.66	0.57	0.64	0.67	0.63	0.62	0.47	0.54	0.63	0.62	0.49	0.50	0.58	0.67	0.45	0.75	0.64	1.00	0.45	0.61	0.67	0.68
	EG	0.45	0.66	0.51	0.54	0.43	0.55	0.51	0.58	0.51	0.55	0.67	0.51	0.58	0.63	0.54	0.66	0.54	0.57	0.45	1.00	0.50	0.49	0.58
PE	0.66	0.58	0.51	0.70	0.59	0.68	0.72	0.58	0.78	0.76	0.62	0.64	0.82	0.66	0.67	0.53	0.64	0.72	0.61	0.50	1.00	0.75	0.55	
PL	0.62	0.59	0.53	0.68	0.63	0.59	0.71	0.62	0.71	0.78	0.61	0.71	0.67	0.62	0.63	0.51	0.66	0.71	0.67	0.49	0.75	1.00	0.64	
KR	0.53	0.63	0.57	0.72	0.64	0.63	0.59	0.50	0.62	0.58	0.54	0.62	0.47	0.61	0.64	0.55	0.70	0.67	0.68	0.58	0.55	0.64	1.00	

Note: Source own elaboration.